

NEW PEDAGOGY FOR MUSIC LESSONS IMPLEMENTATION OF TECHNOLOGIES

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Annotation: This article provides detailed information about the role of music in the life of society, the methods used by teachers of music culture to interest schoolchildren in music lessons.

Keywords: lesson, interest, culture, method, situation, song, music, leader, movement, society, knowledge, thinking.

Music education is also carried out in certain organizational forms, such as classes, excursions, practical and laboratory training, lectures, seminars, dictation, control tests, etc. Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts[1]. In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD - 3391 of November 17, 2017 " On measures to further develop the art of the Uzbek national makom", of May 30, 2019 " On the organization of the activities of the state museum-reserves Sarmishsay", "Shakhrisabz", "Termez" and "Kokand" Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 443 of April 21 [2] , 2020 "On measures to further increase the efficiency of the fine and applied arts" Resolution No. PD - 4688 of May 26, 2020 "Culture Decree No. PD-6000 of May 23 [3]. We understand in a way. Historically, teaching in the group method and individually formed and developing. In any case, the teacher imparts knowledge to the students, guides the process of its acquisition, checks and controls the actions of the students. In modern conditions of education, it is more and more serious to improve traditional methods and to find new methods demands are being made. The introduction of advanced pedagogical technologies, non traditional methods of teaching, in particular, the interactive method, into the educational process of school activities has a good effect.

Pedagogical technology is the optimization of educational forms for the purpose of technical means, human potential and mutual connection taking into account the impact of teaching and knowledge acquisition is a systematic method of identifying, creating and applying processes. Pedagogical technology can be divided into several types:

- general pedagogical technology; private subject technology (for example, music teaching technology);
- local pedagogical technology.

Pedagogical technology is a set of processes, tools, and methods, which appropriately implements pedagogical influence for the formation of predetermined personal qualities in students.

About modern pedagogical methods of music lessons

there are many guides. This method was discovered by advanced music teachers themselves, and it works well.

In particular, "what percentage of the subject is the student when it is explained kept in mind, absorbed by him?" to the natural question the end of the experiment to find the answer will be called the "pyramid of understanding". According to the statement of the topic:

- 10 - 20 percent of it only when listening;

- 30-50 percent if he hears and familiarizes himself with the visual materials on the topic;
 - listens, sings, plays, performs rhythmic movements, tells the topic to his friends, explains, sings with them 60 - 90 of the topic if they are having a conversation about it, if they are arguing percentage will be remembered and assimilated. The student should be able to communicate with his friends, the teacher, and explain his practical training. Only then will the obtained information be strong. By studying and comparing different styles, thinking with colleagues, each teacher can create his own style. If the knowledge of the teacher who implements the program and the textbook is weak, and his professional skills are low, naturally, even if the textbooks are scientifically and methodically thorough, they will not "fly" in the hands of such a teacher, they will be a lifeless piece of paper. will remain, and they are the ones who label the music textbooks as "difficulty in learning the works". Music in the new pedagogical technique it is recommended to use it in necessary places and on its own in the lessons:

Independent work - when a certain group of topics is finished, students are independent in order to organize and consolidate them practical work, engaging in music activities, textbook, music literacy is to develop skills to work with. Pupils to communicate in pairs. It is used to solve an issue related to a work. Teaching students by working in groups.

In this case, the children in the class are divided into groups of five to six people.

Role playing games. Staging a situation specific to the theme of a musical piece, performing it in roles. Musical dictations. One of the current control forms of assessment of the student's knowledge of musical activities.[4]

Choices. The aim is to check and evaluate the acquired knowledge and skills on a certain group of musical topics.

Conferences. It can be held every quarter, as well it can be considered as a type of intermediate control. The students in this report to the class the work they independently wrote in music are presented in the form "Brainstorming". On one selected musical problem communicating with students, doing creative work on this problem invite to go.

"A debate is a debate". There is some music on the theme. The opinions of my students are heard in turn, there are a lot of them thoughtfulness is provided. "Charkhpalak". In this way of increasing student engagement:

- students are divided into groups of six and each the student is given a serial number: 1,2,3,4,5,6;
- each group receives its task from music. Tasks should be different. Group training is essential provided with equipment (textbooks, manuals, notebooks, paper, pencil, pencil, ruler, eraser, etc.);
- groups study the task for 15-20 minutes, it they begin to solve, each group member writes down the result;
- the teacher observes the activity of groups, answers questions, gives advice;
- at the end of time (in the second round) the order numbers are the same the children will join a new group;
- for another 15-20 minutes, each member of the newly formed group tells the other members of this group the task they are solving explains;
- all musical assignments given to the students at the end of the lesson can be tested.[5]

"Research". Based on the acquired knowledge, research is carried out by one or two or three students together on a small musical problem. This issue may or may not be a topic that has yet

to be covered. Working on such issues sharpens the knowledge of a gifted child, encourages him to conduct deep scientific research, and reveals the qualities of a future scientist in the child. Stratification.[6] It is one of the methods of activating teaching, in which children with musical abilities are selected during the teaching process, and it is possible to further develop their musical abilities. Information and communication technology in continuing education, intelligent advanced pedagogical technology with computer capabilities combining, of course, is extremely effective, and this is in the teaching process will be new, high quality and great innovation. Implement this idea one of the real ways to improve is to create electronic textbooks for schools, electronic textbooks can present the subject in the most convenient way to the student, it communicates with the student in an interactive way.[7] The student can study the subject independently and test the knowledge he has acquired on the basis of a test. One of the most important requirements for today's lessons is that the topic selected in each lesson should be scientifically based, that is, the scope of the topic should be determined taking into account the purpose of the lesson and the ability of the students, determining its complexity, the previously studied topic connecting with students, determining the sequence of tasks and independent work for students, determining the equipment needed in the lesson and enriching it with additional visual aids, problem situations in the lesson using additional information technologies (computers) is to create.[8]

Another of the main requirements for the lesson is all didactic tasks to be solved in the lesson itself, assignments to be given at home to be a logical continuation of the knowledge of the student must during the lesson, the teacher checks the physical condition of the student, taking into account creativity, talent, talent, quick thinking need each lesson is analyzed together with the students the result is as expected.

References:

1. Mirkhakimova Feruza Kholdorjon kizi. [Activity of Mutal Burkhanov House Museum](#). CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HISTORY VOLUME: 03 ISSUE: 11 | NOV 2022 (ISSN: 2660-6836). 76-81 pp.
2. Topildiev Odiljon Rakhimjonovich, Mirkhakimova Feruza Kholdorjon kizi. REFORM IN THE FIELD OF CULTURE AND ART IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN. Web of scientist: International scientific research journal. ISSN: 2776-0979, Volume 3, Issue 5, May., 2022.196-198 pp.
3. Mirkhakimova, F. K. (2021). The state museum of history and culture of Namangan region past and today. Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research, 10(8), 84-89.
4. Davletshin M. Psychology of a modern school teacher. - Tashkent, - Uzbekistan, 1999. - P.52
5. Boymirzayev H. "Methodology of learning music". - T.: "Teacher" publishing house, 1995 .- P.14.
6. Sharipova G. "Music and its teaching methodology". - T. "Turon-Iqbal" publishing house, 2011.- P.45.
7. Ishmukhammedov R, Abdukadirov A. Innovative technologies in education. - Tashkent, - Science, 2008. - P.41

8. Tolipova Sh. Pedagogical technologies are a factor in creating a friendly environment. - Tashkent, UNIREF, RTM, XTB, 2005. – P.62

